

Site: ^{SPHINX} TEMPLE Season GS-79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (4e)

Progress of Excavation 28/II/80 R16A2: (4e) appears flush w/ sloping
(to N) surface of (5) (mm. thin) or (6) BLUE GRANITE DUST.

Probably much same or identical w/ (4d). but shows very large
limestone frags. More gypsuumy. This taken out to bedrock
bottom depression for granite sheathing to reveal N edge
of (6) to bedrock floor. II 4/II/80: (4e) here looks to be
essentially same (continuation of) (4d). Region so mottled w/ concentrations of
or admixtures of granite dust, mortar, gypsum, mud spots in R16A1, because
has focus of edge of granite sheathing taken out. (4e) R16A2, same →

Locus Description Mottled Mud Sand Gypsum, Mortar (PINK)
and granite dust.

Location in Square _____

Under Locus (4d) Over Locus Bedrock bottom

Locus Dimensions 7.72 - 7.67 surface

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Granite chips, large limestone
frags, mud spots, pink mortar frags, gypsum spots, pockets
of granite dust

general elevation, brown soil mottled w/ gypsum. Buff soft gypsum and stone chips adhering to face of ledge of bedrock likely remains of original packing between granite sheathing and ledge. Designated (6b) (4c) removed - really is bottom of (4d) here. Contained few scattered charcoal flecks. Several pieces (large) of alabaster.

NOTE. Quantity, fragment sizes, alabaster increased toward bottom (4d) - and (4e).